

A RARE CASE OF DELAYED EMERGENCE FROM ANESTHESIA IN ZYGOMATICO MAXILLARY FRACTURE UNDER GENERAL ANESTHESIA

ABSTRACT

Dexmedetomidine is a selective α_2 -receptor agonist and has sympatholytic, analgesic, and sedative properties.

A 50 years old male patient, weighing 90 kg and 165cm height diagnosed with left zygomatocomaxillary complex (ZMC) fracture with history of Road traffic accident and antiepileptics consumption posted for open reduction and internal fixation under general anesthesia.

Delayed emergence from anesthesia may be due to additive effect of dexmedetomidine and hypothermia on neuromuscular blockade in perioperative period was observed.

The delayed emergence can be avoided by preventing hypothermia, optimising additional dose of dexmedetomidine in perioperative period.

KEYWORD

Dexmedetomidine, emergence from anesthesia, antiepileptics, hypothermia

INTRODUCTION

Dexmedetomidine, an imidazole compound, is the pharmacologically active dextro-isomer of medetomidine that displays specific and selective α_2 adrenoceptor agonism. Activation of the receptors in the brain and spinal cord inhibits neuronal firing, causing hypotension, bradycardia, sedation and analgesia.[1] It is utilised to sedate patients in intensive care units, sedation during the regional anaesthesia and as an adjunct to general anaesthesia. It is recommended to be administered as a two-stage infusion, consisting of a loading dose of 1 mcg/kg over 10 min followed by a maintenance infusion of 0.2-0.7 mcg/kg/h.[2]

Dexmedetomidine is a selective α_2 -receptor agonist and has sympatholytic, analgesic, an sedative properties.[3]

The emergence from anesthesia is the stage of general anesthesia featuring the patient's progression from the unconsciousness status to wakefulness and restoration of consciousness. [4]

To obtain a rapid and reproducible measure of the depth of consciousness, the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) is largely used. The GCS calculates the verbal, movement, and visual responses to stimulation. a GCS < 8 defines a very slow awakening phase and an unconscious patient; on the other hand, a score > 12 is suggestive of awakening.

The propofol dose required for anesthesia and the time to emerge from anesthesia are not affected by the type of neurological disorder, but are affected by antiepileptic use.[5]

CASE PRESENTATION

A 50 years old male patient, weighing 90kg and 165cm height diagnosed with left zygomaticomaxillary complex (ZMC) fracture posted for open reduction and internal fixation under general anesthesia.

Patient had history of road traffic accident 10 days back after which he was unconscious for an hour. He was then started on antiepileptics (Inj. Phenytoin 100 mg Bi times a Day).

In preoperative period he was responding well to the treatment.

In intraoperative period airway was secured with Endotracheal tube no 7 (nasal intubation) after induction with standard dose of Propofol 200 mg (2-2.5 mg/kg) and Rocuronium 70 mg (8-12mg/kg) as a long acting muscle relaxant. In intraoperative period he was administered 90 mcg of dexmedetomidine (1 mcg/kg) as an bolus dose intravenous injection and then infusion of dexmedetomidine 110 mcg (0.4 mcg/kg/hr) for maintenance of anesthesia. 10 mg Injection Rocuronium was injected as a maintenance dose after one hour of induction dose.

Patient was vitally stable during perioperative period with the help of dexmedetomidine and maintenance dosage of rocuronium. After operative procedure, the inhalational anesthetic agents were tapered and oxygenation was started as per the extubation protocol.

Patient was administered Sugammadex as a reversal agent for neuromuscular blockage as per (2mg/kg) but patient showed very little or less response to the drug, hence maximum allowable dose of sugamedex (4mg/kg) was administered.

Unexpectedly patient showed very less response to the drug.

After shifting the patient to surgical intensive care unit the GCS was 6, core body temperature was 95.2°f and to avoid hypothermia warmer was used.

Duration [Post operative]	GCS[3-15]	Core body temperature [°F]	Train Of Four (TOF) Score
0 min	6	95.2	0.4
15 min	7	96.1	0.5
30 min	7	96.8	0.6
60 min	8	98.1	0.6
90 min	8	98.1	0.7
120 min	9	98.2	0.8
150 min	9	98.2	0.8
180 min	10	98.3	0.9

After 30 min the core body temperature was 96.8°f and GCS was 7 with TOF 0.6.

After 60 min post operative period the GCS was 8 and core body temperature was 98.1°f and TOF was 0.6.

After 120 min post operative period the GCS was 9 and core body temperature was 98.2°f and TOF was 0.8.

After 180 min post operative period the GCS was 10 and core body temperature was 98.3^of and TOF was 0.9.

When the patient's GCS was 14 and TOF> 0.9 and there were spontaneous breathing attempts, the extubation went well 3 hours after the surgery. In this case study, the differential diagnosis which we came to know may be overdose of dexmedetomidine, hypothermia or combination of both during the post-operative period.

DISCUSSION

Dexmedetomidine, an imidazole compound, is the pharmacologically active dextroisomer of medetomidine that displays specific and selective α_2 -adrenoceptor agonism. The mechanism of action is unique and differs from those of currently used sedative agents, including clonidine. Activation of the receptors in the brain and spinal cord inhibits neuronal firing, causing hypotension, bradycardia, sedation, and analgesia. [1]

Gertler R. et. al concluded that dexmedetomidine-treated patients were more sedated at the time of arrival in the PACU, emerged more rapidly from anesthesia, required less volatile anesthetic to achieve hemodynamic endpoints, and had greater overall stability in the perioperative period with fewer episodes of tachycardia requiring intervention. [1] But in the present study delayed emergence was observed with the use of dexmedetomidine.

The findings of the present study might be due to overdose of dexmedetomidine.

Dexmedetomidine overdose by bolus injection can result in life-threatening bradycardia and hypotension and may also be associated with miosis. Antipamezole is a non-selective α_2 adrenoceptor antagonist. It rapidly reverses sedation/analgesia induced by dexmedetomidine. However, there are no reports of it being used in dexmedetomidine overdose or toxicity. Moreover, at higher doses, it produces subjective symptoms, such as motor restlessness and hypertension.[3] so antidote of dexmedetomidine antipamezole can be used to avoid further effects of dexmedetomidine and prolonged sedation.

Casella, M.et al stated that hypothermia is frequently encountered under anesthesia. It reduces the metabolism and elimination of drugs and enhances the effects of anesthetics. The affinity of hemoglobin for oxygen increases because hypothermia affects both the dissociation of pH and oxygen, contributing to poor tissue oxygenation. [4]

The lowering of body temperatures in the awakening phase increases oxygen consumption leading to an increase in lactate levels. In addition, the reduced perfusion and metabolism of the drugs increase the duration of the action of sedatives, hypnotics, and some neuromuscular relaxants. In particular, an internal temperature of <33 °C also reduces the minimum alveolar concentration (MAC) value of the inhalation agents. The MAC decreases from 5% to 7% for each °C decrease in internal temperature, enhancing sedation, and lengthening the recovery time. Hypothermia can also induce direct CNS activity depression.[4]

Delayed emergence from anesthesia due to additive effect of dexmedetomidine and hypothermia on neuromuscular blockade in perioperative period.

The delayed emergence can be avoided by preventing hypothermia, optimising additional dose of dexmedetomidine in perioperative period.

CONCLUSION

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